

Multiplexed ultrasonic array system for composite parts inspection.

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ABSTRACT: A high-voltage multichannel ultrasonic system is described as well as its applications to composite parts testing.

The system operates up to 8 channels both in transmission and reception modes, so that only one pulser-receiver is needed.

The transducer device is a 5 MHz broadband eight elements array of multilayer type with a mechanical delay line.

A new analog MUX/DMUX has been designed making possible to switch broadband pulses of large voltage and current peaks.

The manipulator makes easy to scan flat or even T-shaped areas found in the inspection of stringers in aircraft composite parts.

A PC data acquisition system makes possible the on-line simultaneous presentation of B, C and D displays.

1. INTRODUCTION

The non-destructive ultrasonic testing systems for composite materials, such as those used in the space and aircraft industrial sectors, usually make use of manual or mechanical scanning of the sensor devices. This fact limits seriously the inspection speed, specially with large tested structures.

The inspection speed becomes an important problem when the operator must carry out the testing manually, a very usual situation when the inspected sample has a complex geometry. Moreover, the operator must have a certain grade of skill and experience to make an adequate inspection [1].

For these reasons, alternative solutions to the conventional systems must be searched. These alternative solutions must have the following characteristics: enough inspection speed to solve the money and time consuming problems of the usual methods, an adequate

manipulator to scan flat and even T-shaped areas, like those found in inspection of stringers in the aircraft composite parts, and a fast PC based data acquisition system that fully satisfies the growing software and image processing needs of the NDE systems users.

We try to solve the prize and time problems through the use of a 5 MHz broadband eight-elements array transducer, and a MUX/DMUX capable to switch broadband large voltage pulses. Also, we present a manipulator and a fast PC data acquisition system that improve the performances of equivalent systems.

Some constraints must be had in mind to design one of this systems. These constraints affect both the transducer and the electronics. Some examples follow.

After choosing the ultrasonic frequency, the desired lateral and axial resolution will condition the transducer cross-section and the pulse length of the probe. We have selected the optimum transducer materials for inspecting composite materials using water as intermediate coupling medium. Moreover, when thin samples are checked, an acoustic delay line between the transducer and the sample is included. In the case of array transducers, the cross coupling between the elements must be maintained below a certain value - usually 25 dBs - to avoid unwanted image distortions [2]. Finally, the aggressive environmental and operational conditions make necessary to put special attention not only on the probes but also on their construction techniques.

On the other hand, the design difficulties of the driving electronics for these multichannel systems have led to the use of individual pulse-receivers for each array channel [3-4], increasing the price of them. Some factors limit the use of multiplexers for these purposes. First of all, high voltage transmit pulses are required for the transducer excitation. For obtaining a good dynamic range for the testing signals with composite materials, peak values up to 400 volts should be used. Moreover, the low values of the input electrical impedance of the elements of a high frequency piezoelectric transducer, require that the switching circuits between the pulser terminals and the piezoelectric elements, have an on-resistance of less than ten ohms. Neither of the two requirements are satisfied by the commercially available multiplexer circuits [5].

Previous works, including multiplexed arrays for acoustic imaging applications [6-7], describe multiple switches for the sequential acquisition of pulsed ultrasonic signals received from the inspected medium, but they don't report data about the limitations of this kind of devices for multiplexing low impedance transducers from high voltage spike generators.

Now, we are going to describe the characteristics of an industrial system, designed for inspecting several kind of materials, like composites in the space and aircraft industry, that constitutes a quite good solution to overcome the problems previously referred.

2. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The block diagram of the Figure 1, shows the functional configuration of the ultrasonic inspection system that we have developed. It includes an eight element wideband array transducer housed in a versatile manipulator for scanning flat and T-shaped areas, and a PC based data acquisition system with several boards. These boards include a new high voltage analog MUX/DMUX, a commercial high frequency 8 bits A/D converter (100 MHz) with hardware peak detection function, a commercial ultrasonic spike pulser-receiver, and a digital controller to synchronize all the operations. The system software includes advanced display and image processing capabilities, and the operator can change most of the board parameters simply clicking with the mouse on the appropriate item in the computer screen. The software has menus for calibrating the channels, acquiring and printing the results, and

editing previous inspections.

The Figure 2 shows a photo of the system.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the system.

Figure 2. System photograph.

Figure 3 shows the eight elements array transducer. These array works at a central frequency of 4.4 MHz [8]. The general design follows the broadband multilayer concept with three layers. The active one is a PZT-5A piezoelectric ceramic. The backing is made of Araldit-H powdered with Alumina. The only matching layer is made of an epoxy resin. An acoustic delay line (sole) of methacrylate is placed on the matching layer.

Figure 3. The eight elements array transducer.

The cross section dimensions of the array elements are 4.2x5 mm with an interelement space of 0.05 mm, giving a total array aperture of 19x10 mm.

The transducer body is introduced into a housing and sealed with an epoxy resin. All the components and manufacturing procedures have been selected to resist hard environmental conditions.

This array is a part of a three degrees of freedom versatile manipulator, that has an optical encoder to determine exactly the array position over the sample. The manipulator can be designed to fit any particular requirement of special shaped parts, like a curvature radius.

Due to the commercially available integrated analog multiplexers are limited to a maximum input voltage of 50 volts [5], a new high voltage MUX/DMUX has been studied and developed [8-9]. The internal structure of this device is detailed in the Figure 4. The sequential driving of the different transducers is carried out by means of a high voltage analog switch network. This network is able to control the pass of broadband electrical pulses, functioning as a demultiplexer circuit during the emission process and as a multiplexer for the acoustic signals coming back from the tested sample.

This MUX/DMUX network synchronizes the successive excitations of the different transducer elements with the pulse repetition rate of the pulser receiver, by means of a digital controller board. This controller also provides the channel number, selected in each transmit-receive cycle, to the acquisition and display stages for making B, C, and D scans of the inspected piece.

Figure 4. New analog MUX/DMUX.

Figure 5. Perturbation induced in an inactive output by the DMUX input.

Figure 6. Waveforms measured at the input and the on output channel of the DMUX.

The analog switch network of the MUX/DMUX contains eight high voltage channels of four terminals associated to the eight array elements. Each channel has an independent ground return line, connected to an input nodal point in order to avoid electrical cross coupling. Figure 5 shows the small perturbation induced in an inactive output by the high voltage pulse of the DMUX input.

Each MUX/DMUX channel includes a power analog switch controlled by current, as proposed in references [8-9].

The developed MUX/DMUX can perform the bidirectional control of broadband pulses in the high frequency range, with peak amplitudes up to 400 volts exhibiting a very low-on resistance with typical values of the order of 1 ohm. This characteristic permits to carry peak currents as large as 10 amperes during the initial instants of the pulsed excitation of high frequency transducer with high capacity. A very good sensitivity and signal to noise ratios can be obtained at the ultrasonic reception stage with a so low on-resistance. Figure 6 shows the spike waveforms measured at the input and the on output channel of the demultiplexer for two different voltages V_0 of the internal pulser supply.

The switching time between two channels depends on the load connected at their outputs, but it can be reduced to a few hundred of nanoseconds, which lets use this MUX/DMUX device in real time inspections.

The A/D converter and the pulser-receiver boards are commercial ones. They are inserted in the PC's expansion slots, and some of their registers can be addressed by the program in order to change their programmable parameters.

The software is a very flexible one, and includes several image processing, calibrating, printing and displaying capabilities. Most of the system operational parameters can be modified simply clicking the mouse on the selected item. Figure 7 shows a sample calibrating screen.

Figure 8 shows one C-Scan (at the top) and one B-Scan (at the bottom) of a composite part with a delamination. The C-Scans shows the acoustic time of flight from the transducer to the defect coded with colours (the green represents the shorter time, the blue means the larger time). The B-Scan also shows the time of flight. The program provides several representation modes.

Figure 7. Sample calibrating screen.

Figure 8. A C-scan and a B-scan of a composite piece with a delamination.

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